

To Develop Cartesian Robot Intelligent System

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ABSTRACT

This research delves into the contemporary landscape of Cartesian robot systems, aiming to provide a thorough investigation into their design principles, control systems, and diverse applications. Cartesian robots, characterized by their linear motion along three orthogonal axes, have gained prominence across various industries due to their versatility, precision, and efficiency. This study amalgamates theoretical analysis, experimental validation, and real-world applications to present a holistic perspective on the current state of Cartesian robot systems. The research begins with an in-depth exploration of the fundamental design aspects of Cartesian robots, encompassing considerations such as kinematics, dynamics, and structural configurations. By analysing the latest developments in materials, actuators, and sensing technologies, the study aims to identify optimal design parameters that enhance the overall performance and reliability of Cartesian robot systems. The investigation then transitions into the realm of control strategies, emphasizing the significance of advanced control algorithms, adaptive techniques, and real-time feedback systems. Special attention is given to the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms for enhanced adaptability, fault tolerance, and predictive maintenance, thereby contributing to the evolution of Cartesian robots into intelligent and autonomous systems. In addition to technical aspects, the study also addresses economic considerations, evaluating the cost effectiveness and return on investment associated with implementing Cartesian robot systems. Comparative analyses with alternative robotic architectures contribute valuable insights into the strategic decision-making process for industries considering the adoption of Cartesian robots.

Keywords: Cartesian Robot, Control systems, Machine Learning algorithms.

1. Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of industrial automation and robotics, Cartesian robot systems have emerged as pivotal players due to their inherent precision, versatility, and adaptability. Named after the Cartesian coordinate system they operate within, these robots move along three linear axes – X, Y, and Z – allowing for precise and controlled movements in three-dimensional space. This distinctive design facilitates their application across a spectrum of industries, ranging from manufacturing and assembly to healthcare, logistics, and beyond. The Cartesian robot, also known as a gantry or linear robot, stands out for its straightforward mechanical structure, consisting of linear actuators, rails, and a rigid frame. This simplicity contributes to ease of design, scalability, and maintenance, making Cartesian robots an attractive choice for a wide range of applications. The linear motion along each axis enables these robots to navigate large workspaces with unparalleled accuracy, making them indispensable in tasks demanding precision and repeatability. One of the fundamental strengths of Cartesian robots lies in their kinematic simplicity. The direct correspondence between the Cartesian coordinates and the robot's physical movements facilitates precise control and programming. This simplicity not only streamlines the initial design and implementation but also allows for efficient integration with advanced control systems, including real-time feedback mechanisms, adaptive algorithms, and artificial intelligence. The flexibility of Cartesian robot systems is underscored by their capacity to accommodate various end-effectors and tooling, making them suitable for diverse tasks. From high-precision assembly in manufacturing to pick-and-place operations in logistics, Cartesian robots seamlessly adapt to different applications.

Figure 1: Degrees of Freedom for Cartesian Robot

In a Cartesian robot, link joints play a pivotal role in facilitating movement along the X, Y, and Z axes. These joints, often composed of rigid components connected by pivots or sliders, provide the structural framework for precise motion control. Stepper motors, renowned for their accuracy and repeatability, power these link joints, enabling controlled movement in each axis. Through a series of coordinated steps, stepper motors rotate in discrete increments, translating electrical pulses into precise mechanical motion. This synchronization ensures that the Cartesian robot moves with accuracy, crucial for tasks requiring intricate positioning and manipulation. The interplay between link joints and stepper motors forms the backbone of Cartesian robots, facilitating their versatility across a myriad of industrial applications, from 3D printing to CNC machining.

Fig 2: Limit Switch and Timing Belt

Fig 3: X axis Frame

Fig 4: Y axis Frame

1.1 Mechanical Structure and Control System

Cartesian robots typically consist of a rigid frame with linear actuators attached to each axis. These linear actuators facilitate controlled movement along the X, Y, and Z axes. Common types of actuators include ball screws, lead screws, linear motors, or pneumatic cylinders, depending on the application requirements. The frame provides the structural support for the robot, while rails guide the linear motion of each axis. Precision in the design of these components is crucial to ensure accuracy and repeatability in the robot's movements. The Cartesian coordinate system serves as the reference for the robot's movements. The X-axis represents horizontal movement, the Y-axis represents vertical movement, and the Z-axis represents depth or forward/backward movement. Each linear actuator is equipped with a motor that drives the motion along the respective axis. The control system manages the speed, direction, and distance travelled by each motor. Feedback Systems:

Encoders or other position sensors provide real-time feedback on the position of each axis. This feedback is crucial for maintaining accuracy and adjusting movements as needed during operation. Many Cartesian robots employ closed-loop control systems, where feedback from sensors is used to adjust the motor's output, ensuring that the robot achieves and maintains the desired position accurately. The Cartesian robot is programmed to follow specific paths or trajectories in three-dimensional space. Path planning involves determining the sequence of movements required to accomplish a task efficiently. Robots are typically programmed using high-level languages such as Robotic Operating System (ROS), G-code, or vendor-specific languages. The programming includes specifying waypoints, speeds, and other parameters to guide the robot through its tasks. The end-effector is the component attached to the robot that interacts with the workpiece or performs a specific task. It can include grippers, welding tools, cutting tools, or any other tooling depending on the application.

2. Literature Survey

The main aim of this section is to review the literature connected to different types of cartesian robot. Through an extensive review of relevant literature, this review seeks to identify key themes, trends, and gaps in the literature, and to synthesize the findings to advance our understanding of the topic. By examining the strengths and limitations of previous research, this review also aims to highlight areas where further research is needed to address unanswered questions or unresolved issues.

A.Milan et al. [1] demonstrated Linear motion is performed using Technic's ClearPath SD-SK-2311S motors. They are a closed-loop brushless motor system designed to be a drop-in replacement for stepper motors. By using a stepper-like motor, eliminates the need for external encoders, and makes controlling the linear axes quite simple and similar to how a 3D printer is controlled. They were chosen due their high performance and ease of use. For the roll, pitch and yaw axes, three Dynamixel Pro L54-50-500 are used. These motors provide the necessary operating torque to hold a 2kg on the end effector whilst under acceleration. The breakout board needed to include a logic shifter circuits for each of the ClearPath motor pins as the input and output threshold for this microcontroller is only 3.3V and the ClearPath motors needed minimum 5V pulse to operate. In order to interface with the Dynamixel Pro motors, an RS485 module was used so that the Teensy could communicate using the Dynamixel Pro protocol.

Siarhei Autsoy et al. [2] developed a mathematical model of gearbox and analyze additional vibration signals in case of occurring faults Hirata CR is used for work with special attachments, such as electric, pneumatic and magnate grabs. This robot consists of three orthogonal axes and four joints (two linear and two rotation). Gearboxes are set along each axis and consist of the worm gear and tooth belt gear. Grab is connected to the Z and W axes for vertical and rotational movement. The mathematical model of the gearbox is presented as a consistent transfer function of tooth belt gear and worm gear. Additional vibrations occur in joints, gearboxes and other mechanical parts, leading to considerable consequences. This can accelerate metal fatigue, the additional load on the motor, heating of joints and others. The fast Fourier transform, and continuous wavelet transform are used to analyse output signals. The first method is used for getting fast results of spectrum analysis of output signal. The second method is used for transient processes localization. The results of modelling can be used to teach the existing system. For future work, other condition monitoring methods can be used to monitor other failures which may occur during industrial robot operations.

Muhammad Fahmi Miskon et al. [14] presents an innovative approach to enhance user-friendly robot programming, particularly targeting operators with limited robotics expertise. The study introduces a lead-through programming method for a two-degree-of-freedom robotic arm utilizing low-cost incremental encoder feedback. The goal is to enable operators to physically teach robots their trajectories. The experiments conducted validate the method, demonstrating playback accuracy of 96.17% for motor 1 and 97.86% for motor 2. The use of low-cost sensors, such as incremental encoders, contributes to reducing the overall capital and operational costs of robotic technology,

making it more accessible, especially for small and medium enterprises. This method leverages low-cost incremental encoder feedback to enable operators to physically teach robots their trajectories, fostering a more intuitive approach to programming. The research addresses the challenge of making robotic technology more affordable for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) by incorporating low-specification sensors like incremental encoders, thereby reducing both capital and operational costs. The experiments conducted validate the proposed method, showcasing a playback accuracy of 96.17% for motor 1 and 97.86% for motor 2. This approach offers a promising avenue for simplifying robot programming, potentially extending its applicability beyond industrial robots to various other robotic systems with intricate motion requirements.

2.1 Degree of Freedom for Cartesian Robot

Augustine et al. [15] mentioned significance of industrial robots in contemporary manufacturing, highlighting their flexibility and intelligence in executing repetitive tasks with precision and cost-effectiveness. Specifically, the study revolves around the application of robotic manipulators in welding processes, a highly successful use case in industries such as automotive manufacturing. The primary objective of the research is to study and design a five-axis robotic manipulator optimized for welding applications. The authors commence their work by formulating a comprehensive mathematical model of the manipulator. The authors propose that the end effector, which carries the welding torch, traces a circular path during these welding tasks. In the broader context, the study underscores the role of robotic welding in modern industries, where repetitive and precision-intensive tasks are prevalent. The trajectory planning aspect of the study is approached with a focus on maintaining constant velocity during torch movement. The authors propose a method for generating trajectories based on known equations of the path and predetermined velocities. The trajectory planning incorporates both Cartesian and joint space considerations, aiming to control the end effector along the desired path. In conclusion, this paper contributes valuable insights into the mathematical modelling and trajectory planning of a five-axis robotic arm tailored for welding applications. The emphasis on precision, efficiency, and the broader implication for modern industrial processes underscores the significance of the research in the field of robotics and automation.

Jinlong Hu et al. [16] address the challenges in sheet metal bending, a crucial process in industrial manufacturing. The primary objective is to introduce a six-axis Cartesian coordinate robot designed to automate and enhance the efficiency and precision of sheet metal bending operations, aiming to replace manual labour. The authors conduct a thorough analysis of the robot's structural design, employing kinematic simulations through the Automatic Dynamic Analysis of Mechanical System (ADAMS). This simulation-based approach allows for a detailed examination of the robot's overall structure, contributing to a better understanding of its dynamic performance. Subsequent design optimizations are implemented based on these simulations, resulting in the development of a prototype. The paper underscores the significance of this innovative robotic solution in improving stability and efficiency in sheet metal bending machines. Laboratory testing and experiments validate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed robot, marking a noteworthy step toward automating and optimizing sheet metal processing operations. The study not only introduces a practical solution but also contributes valuable insights to the field of robotics in industrial applications. This comparative analysis provides valuable insights into the practical benefits of employing the six-axis Cartesian coordinate robot, establishing its applicability and advantages over traditional manual methods in sheet metal processing. Overall, the research contributes to advancing automation in industrial practices, promoting efficiency, and ensuring safer working environments.

Sotnik S et al. [10] concluded that modern production relies heavily on the integration of automation and sophisticated industrial robots, which are essential for executing diverse tasks with precision and efficiency. These automatic, programmable, and flexible manipulators boast adjustable movement along multiple axes, facilitating the seamless handling of materials, tools, and specialized equipment according to predefined programs. The classification of industrial robots is a critical aspect of understanding their technological capabilities and varied applications in contemporary industries.

This category encompasses versatile robots equipped with one or more working arms that terminate with hinges. Examples include the powerful M-1000iA from FANUC, showcased at the EMO exhibition in Milan, featuring a 1000 kg wrist payload and a remarkable maximum reach of 3253 mm. Notably, it employs a serial link mechanism, providing enhanced versatility in various processing applications, such as drilling, machining of automotive components, and assembly operations. Yaskawa Electric Corporation introduces the GP 215, a 6-axis high-speed robot palletizer with a lifting capacity of 215 kg. Ideal for palletizing corrugated boxes and various heavy assembly operations, this robot represents the evolving landscape of industrial robotics. KUKA's ready2_use packages further demonstrate their commitment to providing preconfigured, coordinated application packages for seamless integration into production equipment.

2.2 Algorithm for motion control

Bharat Bhushan et al. [13] presented Bresenham's line algorithm, a pivotal component in computer graphics, essential for drawing lines on discrete graphics devices like raster video displays, plotters, and image printers. Bresenham's algorithm, serving as the standard for nearly three decades, employs integer operations, including addition, subtraction, and bit shifting, making it adept for real-time interactive applications and high-speed image output. The introduction outlines the algorithm's efficiency and longevity in the field. A hybrid method is introduced, leveraging structural properties of raster lines, particularly runs, to enhance multi-point line generation efficiency. The proposed quadruple-step algorithm reduces decision tests, particularly beneficial in hardware implementations. Rasterization and scan conversion are defined as integral processes in computer graphics, with Bresenham's algorithm highlighted in a block diagram illustrating rendering layer order. The detailed explanation of the algorithm reveals its incremental approach, updating coordinates based on the driving axis and passive axis within a main loop. The example provided demonstrates the application of Bresenham's algorithm in drawing a line from (0, 0) to (5, 3) in device space. The paper identifies keywords such as computer graphics, multimedia, algorithm, Flash movie, ActionScript, rasterization, and scan conversion, underscoring the algorithm's relevance in diverse applications. It concludes by emphasizing Bresenham's algorithm's enduring significance in efficiently generating lines on discrete graphics devices and its integration into modern computer graphics hardware and software libraries.

Hassan et al. [6] concluded that Human-robot interaction has seen significant advancements since the introduction of collaborative robots (COBOT), marking a notable shift towards shared workspaces where robots and humans engage in production activities together. However, this manual welding process poses challenges, including variability in quality, health concerns, and the difficulty of finding skilled specialists. However, navigating a dynamic and complex hybrid environment introduces challenges for trajectory generation and path planning algorithms. These challenges include accounting for robot dynamic and static workspaces, time constraints, and real-time implementation on Industrial Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) or platforms like the Robotic Operating System. The conventional methods of trajectory planning in dynamic environments, such as computing configuration space (C-space) and free path planning algorithms, face computational complexities. In response, this paper introduces a new method named SPADER (Sharing Production Activities in Dynamic Environment) for safe trajectory generation in shared workspaces. SPADER employs a trajectory manager algorithm designed for dynamic environments, facilitating human collaboration with a collaborative robot.

Chen et al. [17] presents a novel Synchronous Cooperative Path Planning (SCPP) algorithm for the coordinated motion control of a robot and positioner in processing complex space curve workpieces, using intersecting line welding as a case study. The system is treated as an 8-degree-of-freedom (DOF) unit, with the objective of planning a synchronous cooperative motion path. The proposed algorithm incorporates constraints, particularly focusing on the Y-axis of the welding torch coordination system, to address intersecting line orientation information. The SCPP is applied to

facilitate the intersecting line welding, and the study evaluates the changes in welding torch orientation and robot joint rotation angles, comparing an improved method with traditional approaches. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the 8 DOF system, ensuring synchronous cooperation throughout the movement without interference. The paper contributes to advancing motion control strategies for robot-positioner collaboration in the industrial context, particularly in the domain of welding complex space curves. The algorithm addresses constraints and evaluates the effectiveness of the 8-DOF system in achieving synchronous cooperation without interference, contributing to motion control advancements in welding complex space curve.

2.3 Control system for Cartesian Robot

Jung et al. [4] focused on the application of disturbance observer (DOB) as a crucial control scheme for addressing uncertainties arising from both internal nonmodel dynamics and external disturbances in motion control applications. Linear disturbance observers (DOB) are implemented through the utilization of inverse models of linear systems and Q-filter design, while nonlinear DOBs are designed using dynamic models of the target system. The accuracy of dynamic models becomes a central concern in DOB implementation due to the inherent difficulty in precisely modeling dynamical systems, especially for highly nonlinear and multi-input multi-output systems like robot manipulators. The robot dynamics equation and Cartesian dynamics equation are provided, emphasizing the impact of external disturbances and nonmodel dynamics. The research delves into the complexities of modeling uncertainties and proposes practical control solutions to enhance the robustness and performance of robot manipulators.

Fernando et al. [20] proposed that joint control theory, while effective, introduces complexities in torque and joint angle-based representations, often posing challenges in intuitive comprehension for end-users. A pivotal issue in joint control theory is the occurrence of singularities, particularly in the boundary workspace, where manipulators reach extreme positions. Addressing this challenge, the researchers highlight the transformative concept of Cartesian control, proposed by S. Arimoto and M. Takegaki in 1981. This paradigm shift allows for the interpretation of robot movements in Cartesian space, providing a more intuitive understanding for end-users. Singularities, which may hinder velocity control and pose mathematical challenges, are mitigated through the use of the Jacobian Transposed matrix, offering enhanced control capabilities. The significance of this research lies in its contribution to the field of robotic manipulators, emphasizing the importance of transitioning from joint-based control theories to Cartesian control for improved user comprehension and control efficiency. The chapter underscores the necessity of understanding the mathematical tools for analyzing robot movements in Cartesian space, enabling the development of robust control structures and dynamic models. Overall, the research review sets the stage for exploring position control in robot manipulators with a focus on Cartesian space and provides a foundation for further advancements in this domain.

S. Autso et al. [3] used Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) to analyze additional vibrations in a robot, specifically focusing on the Hirata CR. The degree of belt tension is a key parameter under investigation, with control modes such as teach, and check modes selected for experimentation. The spectrum analysis results, highlight significant oscillations in the check mode, attributed to the wide range of speed the robot experiences during acceleration (up to 700 mm/sec). Notably, the X-axis exhibits the most substantial vibrations. The study delves into the impact of over/low belt tension faults, revealing that over-tension can result in undesirable vibrations and an emergency stop during experiments.

Puran Singh et al. [12] Design and development of a robotic arm equipped with a gripper and end effectors for spot welding applications. The underlying concept involves creating a system with multiple interacting subsystems that collaboratively engage with the environment. In the realm of robotics, end effectors serve as devices located at the end of a robotic arm, specifically designed for interaction with the surroundings. In the contemporary manufacturing landscape, especially in the automobile industry, technological advancements and competition necessitate efficient and flexible production processes. Automation, achieved through various machines, including Computer

Numerical Control (CNC) and conveyors, plays a crucial role in meeting these requirements. Robots, employed for tasks like spot welding, painting, assembly, and handling parts, contribute to faster and more accurate work.

3. Conclusion

The successfully developed Cartesian robot performs a wide array of tasks without the burden of extensive reprogramming or hardware modifications. Its agility in adapting to diverse requirements ensures seamless integration into various industrial settings. Through meticulous design and strategic resource management, the Cartesian robot solution has been crafted to be exceptionally cost-effective. By prioritizing affordability, even for smaller businesses or organizations, this solution democratizes access to advanced automation technology, fostering innovation and competitiveness across industries. Intuitive interfaces and controls empower operators with the tools to swiftly configure tasks, significantly reducing setup time and optimizing workflow continuity. With a focus on user-centric design, the Cartesian robot's programming process has been streamlined to minimize complexity and maximize efficiency. This emphasis on user-friendliness ensures rapid deployment and seamless integration into existing operational frameworks. This collaborative efficiency not only enhances productivity but also promotes a harmonious working environment, where humans and robots collaborate seamlessly to achieve shared goals. The journey doesn't end with the current achievements. Continuous improvement and iteration are key principles guiding the evolution of the Cartesian robot technology. Feedback from users and ongoing research will drive innovation, leading to even more advanced functionalities and applications in the future. Continuous improvement lies at the heart of our commitment to excellence in Cartesian robot technology. Building on our current achievements, we remain dedicated to refining and enhancing every aspect of the robotic system. Through ongoing research, rigorous testing, and user feedback, we strive to identify areas for optimization and innovation.

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